

Empirical Study: Correlation Of Intellectual, Emotional Intelligence, And Adversity To Learning Outcomes

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to determine the correlation of intellectual, emotional, and adversity quotient to learning outcomes. This study uses a descriptive quantitative approach and multiple correlations, while the data collection techniques are through questionnaires and documents. Based on data analysis shows that the value of sig. f change is $0.000 < 0.05$ and the R value is 0.809, meaning that Intellectual Intelligence (X1), Emotional Intelligence (X2), and Adversity Quotient (X3) have a simultaneous and significant relationship to learning outcomes (Y) with a very strong relationship criteria. Thus, it can be concluded that the higher the intellectual intelligence, emotional intelligence, and adversity quotient, the learning outcomes will increase.

Introduction

In the process of improving the quality of human resources, it is closely related to learning outcomes, and this is a problem for educational institutions, especially educators (Prasetya, 2019). Education is a process of balance to develop individual potential which can be seen from various aspects such as intellectual, emotional, physical, spiritual and social (Laili, 2021). Sarid, A. (2017) explained that education is a continuous practice consisting of purposively structured learning processes aimed at the realisation of ends that are consciously derived from a certain conception of the 'good'.

Wahyu et al. believes that, quality education will be born from schools and universities that have high quality and are committed to improving the quality and learning outcomes (W B Sulfemi, 2019). According to Benny et al, there are several factors that affect achievement or learning outcomes, namely internal factors that come from within students such as intelligence/intelligence, health, emotions, motivation, interests and talents while external comes from outside students (Prasetya, 2019). Andoko et al revealed that one of the factors that influence learning outcomes is intelligence (Mirnawati & Basri, 2018). Referring to constructivism theory, there are many factors that influence learning outcomes, so it is used as a study in this research.

Based on this, the formulation of the problem in this study is; is there a correlation between intellectual, emotional and adversity quotient on learning outcomes. The results of the researcher's search found that there was no research that analyzed in detail the correlation or relationship of the three components of intelligence, intellectual, emotional and adversity to learning outcomes. Previous research only analyzed the influence or relationship between intellectual, emotional, spiritual intelligence on learning outcomes carried out by students; Andri (2018), Budi W et al (2018), Lorenzo (2018) and Akhdan (2018), Ilham (2017), Adoko (2018), Nurul (2021), Wardani (2019) and Puspitacandri, A. et.al. (2020). The advantage of this research is that it examines and reveals in detail about the intelligence possessed by students, which is very useful for lecturers in planning, implementing, and evaluating the process of students' abilities, so that it can affect learning outcomes.

Literature Review

Learning Outcomes

Learning is a relatively permanent change in behavior resulting from past experience or from planned and structured learning (Dwijayani, 2019). Learning outcomes can be interpreted as something done by students where previously it could not be done, learning outcomes can be in the form of actions, values, understanding, attitudes and skills (Andriani & Rasto, 2019). Referring to Bloom's Taxonomy theory, learning outcomes can be

achieved through three domains, namely cognitive, affective, and psychomotor (Wahyu Bagja Sulfemi, 2018). Gronlund in Beny, learning outcomes are grouped into; (1) knowledge, (2) understanding, (3) thinking skills, (4) skills in appearance, (5) communication skills, (6) numeracy skills, (7) learning skills while working, (8) socializing, (9) attitude, (10) interest, (11) adjustment (Prasetya, 2019).

Intellectual Intelligence

Intellectual intelligence is the general ability possessed by individuals in distinguishing one's qualities from others (Iqbal et al., 2020). According to Binet and Simon in A. Priadi, there are three components that belong to a person's intelligence, namely: 1) the ability to direct thoughts and actions, the ability to change the direction of action, the ability to criticize oneself (Andri, 2018). Galtom in Iqbal et al (Iqbal et al., 2020) explained that intellectual intelligence is the cognitive ability possessed to adapt effectively to an ever-changing environment and is influenced by genetic factors. Lorenzo et al argue that intellectual intelligence is analysis, logic, and ratio. This intelligence is an ability to receive, store and process information into a fact (Mamangkey et al., 2018). Ludigdo in Akhdan revealed the results of his research that Intellectual intelligence simultaneously or partially has a significant effect on ethical attitudes (Dewi & Wirakusuma, 2018). Geleman argues that intellectual intelligence only contributes 20% in determining success (Juliani, 2018).

Emotional Intelligence

Every student certainly has intelligence, but what distinguishes it is the level of intelligence in each student (Mirnawati & Basri, 2018). John stated that emotional intelligence includes self-control, strength and ability to motivate oneself to be able to survive frustration, and have the ability to control one's heart and emotions (Siswa & Sman, 2020). Another statement from Andoko et al., Emotional intelligence is the ability to feel, understand, selectively apply emotional power and sensitivity as a source of energy, so that with emotional intelligence students are able to respect themselves and others and respond appropriately (Mirnawati & Basri, 2018). Made et al. revealed the results of research that emotional intelligence plays a very important role in the success of students at the university level (Suwi Novita Devi et al., 2020). According to Benny, emotional intelligence is a collection of social intelligence by involving the ability to monitor the feelings and emotions of oneself and others, Beny also classifies the form of emotional quality to achieve success, including; (1) empathy, (2) expressing and understanding feelings, (3) controlling anger, (4) independence, (5) adjusting ability, (6) discussion (7) interpersonal problem solving ability, (8) strength, (9) solidarity, (10) friendliness, (11) respect (Prasetya, 2019).

There are many studies on emotional intelligence on learning outcomes including, Andoko (2018), Beny (2019), Ilham (2017), the conclusion of this study revealed that emotional intelligence greatly affects student learning outcomes and can even help overcome psychological barriers in learning.

Adversity Intelligence

Adversity is misery and misfortune which is a determining factor for one's success, adversity intelligence is defined as the ability of a person's fighting power to survive in the face of problems or difficulties (Wardani, 2019). Pertiwi et al. also argue that adversity intelligence is the ability of individuals to survive and find solutions to the problems they face, so this ability is very important in learning (Pertiwi et al., 2019). Adversity intelligence is the science of resilience that is expected by every individual to have adversity intelligence so that they can recognize their own difficulties and be able to manage them into a potential solution (Laili, 2021). Adversity intelligence is the fighting power that exists within the individual which can be seen from the character of control and adjustment in life (Manado, 2020). In line with Marianah's opinion, adversity intelligence is an individual's intelligence in overcoming any problems that arise (Quotient, 2019). Hartosujono in Wardani, classifies adversity intelligence into 4 aspects, namely; (1) the ability to face difficulties and overcome the problems being faced, (2) the ability to estimate the time limit of a person to overcome difficulties and give up on difficulties, (3) the ability to exceed expectations for performance and potential, (4) the ability to predict to give up on difficulties (Wardani, 2019). Adversity intelligence is the ability to perceive, face and overcome difficulties (King, F.J., Goodson, L. and Rohani, 2013). Nadiyah et al. revealed the factors that influence adversity intelligence, namely; (1) talent, (2) willpower, (3) intelligence, (4) health, (5) personality characteristics, (6) genetics, (7) education and self-confidence (Susanto & Sofyani, 2019). Nadiyah also revealed that there are five aspects contained in the resilience of adversity; (1) willing to take risks, (2) overcoming fear, (3) facing challenges, (4) maintaining vision, (5) working hard to finish (Susanto & Sofyani, 2019).

Research Methods

This study uses a descriptive quantitative approach and correlation. Data collection techniques through questionnaires via google form. This study consists of four variables, the 3 independent variables consist of intellectual intelligence (X1), emotional intelligence (X2), adversity quotient (X3). The dependent variable is student learning outcomes (Y), the indicators studied are 3 domains of Bloom's taxonomic intelligence, namely; cognitive, affective, and psychomotor. The research population is all Education Management Students at the Faculty of Teacher Training and Education Class of 2018 totaling 179 people. The sample used is 25% of the total population, namely $\frac{25}{100} \times 179 = 44,75 \approx 45$ (Supriyanto & Iswandari, 2017). Data collection techniques are: Questionnaires and Documentation. After the data are collected, then the instrument and validity are tested through Pearson's product moment on the values between the X variable and Y variable. The reliability test of this research uses the SPSS program (*Statistical Product and Service Solution*).

Results and Discussion

The data presented is in the form of raw data which is processed using descriptive statistical techniques and multiple correlations. The research data is the variable data of Intellectual Intelligence (X1), Emotional Intelligence (X2), Adversity Quotient (X3), and Learning Outcomes (Y).

Data Description of Intellectual Intelligence (X1), Emotional Intelligence (X2), Adversity Quotient (X3), and Learning Outcomes (Y).

Table 1
Summary of Descriptive Statistics Results

		Intellectual Intelligence (X1)	Emotional Intelligence X2)	Adversity Quotient (X3)	Learning Outcomes (Y)
N	Valid	45	45	45	45
	Missing	0	0	0	0
Mean		84,47	83,22	87,76	86,11
Std. Error of Mean		,952	1,182	1,089	,953
Median		84,22 ^a	84,67 ^a	87,75 ^a	85,83 ^a
Mode		85	87	93	80 ^b
Std. Deviation		6,384	7,928	7,306	6,390
Variance		40,755	62,859	53,371	40,828
Skewness		,521	-,702	-,114	,111
Std. Error of Skewness		,354	,354	,354	,354
Kurtosis		-,292	,274	-1,205	-,886
Std. Error of Kurtosis		,695	,695	,695	,695
Range		25	34	25	24
Minimum		75	61	75	75
Maximum		100	95	100	99
Sum		3801	3745	3949	3875

(Source: Processed Data, 2021)

The summary of descriptive statistics results above explains as follows:

1. The description of intellectual intelligence data (X1) shows that the average value reaches 84.47 with a standard deviation of 6.384. This means that Intellectual Intelligence (X1) is categorized as moderate or good enough.
2. The description of emotional intelligence data (X2) shows that the average value reaches 83.22 with a standard deviation of 7.928. Based on this, it states that Emotional Intelligence (X2) is categorized as moderate or good enough.

3. The description of the adversity quotient (X3) data shows that the average value reaches 87.76 with a standard deviation of 7.306. This means that the Adversity Quotient (X3) is categorized as moderate or good enough.
4. The description of the data of learning outcomes (Y) shows that the average value reaches 86.11 with a standard deviation of 6.390. This states that the learning outcomes (Y) are categorized as moderate or good enough.

Normality test

The normality test was conducted to determine whether the dependent variable and the independent variable both had a normal distribution or not. The results of the normality test are presented in the table below.

Table 2
Summary of Normality Test Result
Kolmogorov-Smirnov^a Shapiro-Wilk

Variable	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk			Description
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.	
Intellectual Intelligence	,111	45	,200*	,959	45	,116	Normal
Learning Outcomes	,099	45	,200*	,973	45	,384	
Emotional Intelligence	,105	45	,200*	,952	45	,063	Normal
Learning Outcomes	,099	45	,200*	,973	45	,384	
Adversity Quotient	,119	45	,116	,952	45	,059	Normal
Learning Outcomes	,099	45	,200*	,973	45	,384	

*. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Based on the significance value of Shapiro Wilk the dependent variable and the independent variable above, it is known that the value of Sig. > 0.05 then it is concluded that the data is normally distributed.

Test Results of Hypotheses

The statistical technique used in the correlation analysis in this study uses the correlation of Pearson Product Moment.

Formulation of Hypothesis 1

H₀ = There is no relationship between Intellectual Intelligence and learning outcomes

H_a = There is a Relationship between Intellectual Intelligence and Learning Outcomes

ANOVA Table							
			Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Learning Outcomes * Intellectual Intelligence	Between Groups	(Combined)	1534,778	22	69,763	5,865	,000
		Linearity	1063,038	1	1063,038	89,376	,000
		Deviation from Linearity	471,739	21	22,464	1,889	,073
	Within Groups	261,667	22	11,894			
	Total	1796,444	44				

Correlations		
	Intellectual Intelligence	Learning Outcomes
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,000
	N	45
	Pearson Correlation	,769**
Learning Outcomes	Sig. (2-tailed)	,000
	N	45

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The SPSS Output Analysis above explains as follows:

1. If the significance is > 0.05 , then H_0 accepted If significance < 0.05 , then H_0 rejected. In this case, it can be seen that the Pearson Correlation is 0.769 with a significance of 0.000. Since the significance is $0.000 < 0.05$, then H_0 rejected, means H_a is accepted. This means that there is a significant relationship between Intellectual Intelligence and learning outcomes.
2. Based on the value of r count $0.769 > r$ table 0.2483, it is concluded that there is a correlation.
3. Looking at the strength of the relationship, the correlation coefficient of 0.769 means that the level of strength of the correlation between Intellectual Intelligence and learning outcomes is strong.
4. Looking at the type of direction, the coefficient number is positive, namely 0.769, the relationship between the two variables is unidirectional, it can be interpreted that the Intellectual Intelligence is increasing, the student learning outcomes will also increase.

Formulation of Hypothesis 2

H_0 = There is no relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Learning Outcomes

H_a = There is a Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Learning Outcomes

ANOVA Table							
			Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Learning Outcomes * Emotional Intelligence	Between Groups	(Combined)	1164,944	24	48,539	1,537	,166
		Linearity	359,316	1	359,316	11,380	,003
		Deviation from Linearity	805,629	23	35,027	1,109	,410
	Within Groups	631,500	20	31,575			
	Total		1796,444	44			

Correlations			
		Emotional Intelligence	Learning Outcomes
Emotional Intelligence	Pearson Correlation	1	,447**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		,002
	N	45	45
Learning Outcomes	Pearson Correlation	,447**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,002	
	N	45	45

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The SPSS Output Analysis above explains as follows:

1. If the significance is > 0.05 , then H_0 accepted If significance < 0.05 , then H_0 rejected. In this case, it can be seen that the Pearson Correlation is 0.447 with a significance of 0.002. Because the significance is $0.002 < 0.05$, then H_0 rejected, means H_a is accepted. This means that there is a significant relationship between Emotional Intelligence and learning outcomes.
2. Based on the value of r count $0.447 > r$ table 0.2483, it is concluded that there is a correlation
3. Looking at the strength of the relationship, the correlation coefficient of 0.447 means that the level of strength of the correlation between Emotional Intelligence and learning outcomes is moderate.
4. Looking at the type of direction, the coefficient number is positive, namely 0.447, the relationship between the two variables is unidirectional, it can be interpreted that Emotional Intelligence is increasing, student learning outcomes will also increase.

Formulation of Hypothesis 3

H_0 = there is no relationship between adversity quotient on learning outcomes

H_a = there is a relationship between adversity quotient on learning outcomes

ANOVA Table							
			Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Learning Outcomes * Adversity Quotient	Between Groups	(Combined)	1173,861	25	46,954	1,433	,212
		Linearity	211,786	1	211,786	6,463	,020

	Deviation from Linearity	962,076	24	40,086	1,223	,330
Within Groups		622,583	19	32,768		
Total		1796,444	44			

Correlations			
		Adversity Quotient	Learning Outcomes
Adversity Quotient	Pearson Correlation	1	,343*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		,021
	N	45	45
Learning Outcomes	Pearson Correlation	,343*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,021	
	N	45	45

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The SPSS Output Analysis above explains as follows:

1. If the significance is > 0.05 , then H_0 is accepted. If the significance is < 0.05 , then H_0 is rejected. In this case, it can be seen that the Pearson Correlation is 0.447 with a significance of 0.021. Because the significance is $0.021 < 0.05$, then H_0 is rejected, meaning H_a is accepted. This means that there is a significant relationship between Adversity Quotient and learning outcomes.
2. Based on the value of r count $0.343 > r$ table 0.2483 , it is concluded that there is a correlation
3. Looking at the strength of the relationship, the correlation coefficient of 0.343 means that the level of strength of the correlation between Adversity Quotient and learning outcomes is low.
4. Looking at the type of direction, the coefficient number is positive, namely 0.343, the relationship between the two variables is unidirectional, it can be interpreted that the Adversity Quotient is increased, the student learning outcomes will also increase.

Multiple Correlation Test

Formulation of Hypothesis 4

H_0 = There is a correlation between intellectual intelligence, emotional intelligence, and adversity intelligence with learning outcomes

H_a = There is no correlation between intellectual intelligence, emotional intelligence, and adversity intelligence with learning outcomes

Model Summary									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	,809 ^a	,655	,630	3,889	,655	25,926	3	41	,000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Adversity Quotient, Intellectual Intelligence, Emotional Intelligence

The SPSS Output Analysis above explains as follows:

1. Value of Sig. F Change of $0.000 < 0.05$, it can be concluded that the variables of Intellectual Intelligence (X1), Emotional Intelligence (X2), Adversity Quotient (X3) have a significant relationship to learning outcomes (Y) simultaneously. There is a correlation between intellectual intelligence, emotional intelligence, and Adversity Quotient with student learning outcomes.
2. The value of R (correlation coefficient) is 0.809, it can be concluded that the level of relationship between Intellectual Intelligence (X1), Emotional Intelligence (X2), Adversity Quotient (X3) Has a significant relationship to learning outcomes (Y) simultaneously has a very strong relationship.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the research which includes the variables of Intellectual Intelligence (X1), Emotional Intelligence (X2), Adversity Quotient (X3), and learning outcomes (Y) the empirical truth can be accepted as follows:

1. There is a significant relationship between Intellectual Intelligence and learning outcomes, because the significance is $0.000 < 0.05$. Based on the value of r count $0.769 > r$ table 0.2483 , it can be concluded that there is a correlation. Looking at the strength of the relationship, the correlation coefficient of 0.769 means that the level of strength of the correlation between Intellectual Intelligence and learning outcomes is

- strong. Looking at the type of direction, the coefficient number is positive, namely 0.769, the relationship between the two variables is unidirectional; it can be interpreted that the Intellectual Intelligence increases, the student learning outcomes will also increase.
2. There is a significant relationship between Emotional Intelligence and learning outcomes. Because the significance is $0.002 < 0.05$. Based on the value of r count $0.447 > r$ table 0.2483 , it is concluded that there is a correlation. Looking at the strength of the relationship, the correlation coefficient of 0.447 means that the level of strength of the correlation between Emotional Intelligence and learning outcomes is moderate. Looking at the type of direction, the coefficient number is positive, namely 0.447 , the relationship between the two variables is unidirectional, it can be interpreted that Emotional Intelligence is increasing, student learning outcomes will also increase.
 3. There is a significant relationship between Adversity Quotient and learning outcomes. Because the significance is $0.021 < 0.05$. Based on the value of r count $0.343 > r$ table 0.2483 , it is concluded that there is a correlation. Looking at the strength of the relationship, the correlation coefficient of 0.343 means that the level of strength of the correlation between Adversity Quotient and learning outcomes is low. Looking at the type of direction, the coefficient number is positive, namely 0.343 , the relationship between the two variables is unidirectional, it can be interpreted that the Adversity Quotient is increasing, the student learning outcomes will also increase.
 4. Sig. F Change of $0.000 < 0.05$, it can be concluded that the variables of Intellectual Intelligence (X1), Emotional Intelligence (X2), Adversity Quotient (X3) have a significant relationship to learning outcomes (Y) simultaneously. There is a correlation between intellectual intelligence, emotional intelligence, and Adversity Quotient with learning outcomes. The value of R (correlation coefficient) is 0.809 , it can be concluded that the level of relationship between Intellectual Intelligence (X1), Emotional Intelligence (X2), Adversity Quotient (X3) Has a significant relationship to learning outcomes (Y) simultaneously has a very strong relationship.

Recommendations

The results of the research above explain that there is a significant relationship among intellectual, emotional and adversity quotient on learning outcomes, this indicates the role of universities to provide a conducive environment and the role of lecturer professionalism in the lecture process as an effort to improve student learning outcomes.

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